

Lumbopelvic Dysfunction, Psoas-Piriformis Tone and Deep Gluteal Syndrome

Proposal for an Integrated Clinical Model Using EVM

Francesco Alicata

Version 1.1 / English version 1.0

May 2, 2026

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19977908

English translation

Methodological note

This work does not represent a controlled clinical study, but an observational proposal derived from clinical practice. The model described has descriptive and interpretative purposes: it aims to identify a recurrent postural-functional pattern and to propose possible criteria for assessment and treatment.

The observations reported do not constitute definitive statistical validation and require further confirmation through structured case series, observational studies or dedicated clinical research.

Premise

In clinical practice, a pattern is observed with some frequency that is characterized by lumbopelvic/iliosacral dysfunction, functional asymmetry of the lower limb, increased tone of the psoas and deep gluteal compartment, and variable symptoms: low back pain, gluteal pain, sciatic-like radiation, trochanteric pain and reduced tolerance to sporting activity.

This pattern may be particularly evident in athletes, especially in sports involving changes of direction, asymmetric foot placement, braking, rapid rotation and variable playing surfaces, such as futsal. In sedentary subjects, the same alteration may more often present as low back pain, stiffness, deep gluteal pain or intolerance to prolonged sitting.

Clinical observation suggests that the problem is not exclusively articular, but also involves a tonic-proprioceptive component, in which the psoas, piriformis and deep hip rotators may contribute to maintaining the dysfunctional pattern.

Observed clinical pattern

The typical pattern may include:

- lumbopelvic or iliosacral dysfunction;
- apparent functional short leg;
- increased tone of the psoas and piriformis;
- lumbar or lumbosacral pain;
- deep gluteal pain;

- possible sciatic-like radiation;
- lateral hip or trochanteric pain;
- reduced tolerance to running, changes of direction or prolonged sitting;
- tendency toward recurrence of gluteal pain in sedentary subjects.

The term "piriformis syndrome" may be reductive. In many cases, it is more appropriate to speak of deep gluteal syndrome, meaning a disorder of the deep gluteal compartment in which the piriformis may be involved, but does not necessarily represent the only responsible structure.

Functional interpretation

Lumbopelvic dysfunction may alter loading of the lower limb and produce a muscular adaptation. In this context, the psoas and piriformis may develop persistent defensive tone.

Manual treatment of the pelvis can rapidly correct the functional alteration; however, if the protective muscular tone is not reduced, the system may retain a memory of the previous pattern.

The central point of the model is therefore the following:

recurrence does not necessarily depend on ineffective manual correction, but on persistent muscular tone that tends to maintain or reactivate the dysfunctional pattern.

From this perspective, treatment should not be limited to articular release, but should include a phase aimed at reducing tone in the muscular structures involved.

Evolution of the treatment

In an initial phase, after manual lumbopelvic release, treatment was completed with prolonged manual techniques such as pompage and myofascial work on the psoas, piriformis and deep gluteal musculature.

This approach often required a relatively long therapeutic cycle: in some cases, several weeks of treatment were necessary, up to approximately one and a half months, with an average frequency of two sessions per week.

Subsequently, EVM was introduced with the aim of obtaining a reduction in muscular tone in a shorter time and with greater reproducibility.

EVM is not intended as a substitute for manual release, but as a subsequent phase of neuromuscular stabilization.

The therapeutic sequence can be summarized as follows:

manual release corrects the lumbopelvic system; EVM reduces the tone that could favor a return to the previous pattern.

Application protocol

The protocol used includes:

- manual lumbopelvic/iliosacral release;

- application of EVM to the deep gluteal compartment, particularly in the piriformis region;
- treatment of the psoas in the inguinal region, between the pelvis and femur;
- use of decreasing frequencies: 50 Hz, 40 Hz, 30 Hz;
- duration of approximately 3 minutes for each frequency;
- bilateral application;
- average cycle of approximately 3 sessions in typical cases.

Compared with the previous approach based on pompage and prolonged manual work, which could require several weeks of treatment, the introduction of EVM seems to allow the same clinical objective to be reached more rapidly: reduction of defensive tone and stabilization of the lumbopelvic correction.

Importance of the psoas treatment site

A relevant technical element is the site of application on the psoas.

Treatment is performed in the inguinal region, between the pelvis and femur, with controlled and progressive pressure that is always modulated according to the patient's response.

Application higher up, above the pelvis, does not appear to produce the same stabilizing effect. This suggests that the treatment site is not a secondary detail, but an essential component of the protocol.

Because of the anatomical delicacy of the inguinal region, the application must respect criteria of prudence:

- avoid aggressive compression;
- do not work directly on the femoral triangle;
- interrupt the treatment in case of paresthesia, radiating pain or abnormal neurovascular sensations;
- carefully evaluate patients with inguinal or femoral hernias, recent surgical outcomes, anticoagulant therapy, masses, painful lymph nodes or vascular fragility.

Desired effect

The effect of EVM is not interpreted as simple mechanical muscle lengthening.

The main objective is the downregulation of defensive tone.

The desired effects are:

- reduction of protective hypertonicity;
- proprioceptive modulation;
- reduction of local mechanical sensitivity;
- improved load tolerance;
- stabilization of the lumbopelvic correction;
- reduction in the tendency toward functional recurrence.

The most appropriate formulation is therefore:

it is not simply a matter of lengthening a muscle, but of reducing chronic defensive tone.

Relationship with deep gluteal syndrome

The observed symptoms often overlap with what is known as deep gluteal syndrome.

This condition includes deep gluteal pain, sometimes associated with sciatic-like radiation, not primarily discogenic, and related to irritation or compression of the sciatic nerve and soft tissues in the deep gluteal space.

In the proposed model, the deep gluteal compartment is not considered in isolation, but within a broader system that includes:

- pelvis;
- sacroiliac/iliosacral joint;
- psoas;
- piriformis;
- deep rotators;
- gluteal muscles;
- lumbopelvic control;
- load tolerance.

This approach makes it possible to distinguish deep gluteal pain from a simple "piriformis syndrome" and to frame it within a more functional and integrated view.

Recurrence of the block and gluteal flare-up

After complete treatment, true recurrence of the lumbopelvic block appears to become rare. When it reappears, it tends to be associated with a new triggering event, such as:

- fall;
- trauma;
- violent sporting gesture;
- major overload;
- new mechanical alteration.

The behavior of the deep gluteal compartment is different.

In some patients, especially sedentary subjects, a tendency toward painful or tonic reactivation of the deep gluteal region may persist over time, even months later. In these cases, the pelvis remains stable, but tension, local pain, sitting discomfort or mild sciatic-like symptoms reappear.

It is therefore useful to distinguish two phenomena:

Pattern	Pelvis	Symptoms	Interpretation
True recurrence of the block	Altered again	Low back pain, gluteal pain, sciatic-like radiation, functional asymmetry	New trauma, fall, overload or mechanical event
Deep gluteal flare-up	Stable	Gluteal pain/tension, sitting discomfort, mild sciatic-like symptoms	Local tonic reactivation of the deep gluteal compartment

This distinction is important because the return of gluteal pain does not necessarily indicate a new iliosacral dysfunction.

Thoracolumbar-gluteal component of the flare-up

In some patients, when a flare-up of the deep gluteal compartment occurs, lateral tenderness may also be detected in the region of the last thoracic vertebrae or at the thoracolumbar junction.

This finding does not necessarily coincide with recurrence of the lumbopelvic block. In these cases, the pelvis may remain stable while pain and tone reactivate in the deep gluteal compartment.

The association between gluteal pain and low thoracolumbar pain may be interpreted as co-activation of the thoracolumbopelvic system, rather than as a direct metameric relationship with the piriformis. The piriformis belongs predominantly to a sacral neurological territory, whereas the low thoracolumbar region may be involved through functional, fascial or reflex mechanisms.

Potentially involved structures may include:

- thoracolumbar fascia;
- quadratus lumborum;
- low paravertebral musculature;
- thoracolumbar junction;
- thoracolumbar posterior rami;
- superior cluneal nerves;
- functional connections between trunk, pelvis and gluteal compartment.

This component may explain why, in some patients, the gluteal flare-up does not manifest only as local piriformis or deep rotator pain, but also as low lateral thoracolumbar pain.

It is therefore useful to distinguish three situations:

Pattern	Pelvis	Deep gluteal compartment	Low thoracolumbar region
True recurrence of the block	Altered	Often painful	Possible compensation
Simple gluteal flare-up	Stable	Painful/hypertonic	Absent or minimal
Gluteal flare-up with thoracolumbar-gluteal component	Stable	Painful/hypertonic	Low lateral thoracic/thoracolumbar tenderness

From a clinical point of view, this distinction is useful because it avoids interpreting every painful reactivation as a new iliosacral dysfunction. In the presence of a stable pelvis, deep gluteal pain and

low lateral thoracolumbar pain, the pattern may be interpreted as a tonic-functional reactivation of the thoracolumbar-gluteal system.

Difference between athletes and sedentary subjects

In trained athletes, the gluteal compartment seems to maintain good load tolerance more easily. Regular physical activity supports strength, mobility, lumbopelvic control and tissue adaptability.

In sedentary subjects, prolonged sitting, reduced hip mobility, lower gluteal activation and poor preparation for loading may favor periodic reactivations of the deep gluteal compartment.

For this reason, local maintenance work may be useful in sedentary subjects.

Maintenance strategy

After treatment, especially in sedentary patients or in those with a long history of gluteal pain, a preventive strategy may be useful, based on:

- deep self-massage of the gluteal region with an irregular ball;
- hip mobility;
- progressive reactivation of the gluteus maximus and gluteus medius;
- reduction of prolonged sitting;
- gradual preparation before periods of greater physical effort;
- periodic check-up in case of symptom reactivation.

The rationale is not to keep the pelvis "released", but to reduce the tendency of the deep gluteal compartment to reactivate a hypertonic pattern.

Summary of the clinical model

The model can be summarized in the following points:

1. some patients present with lumbopelvic dysfunction associated with functional asymmetry of the lower limb;
2. the psoas, piriformis and deep rotators may develop persistent defensive tone;
3. manual release alone can rapidly correct the pattern, but may not always be sufficient to stabilize it if tone persists;
4. EVM applied to the psoas and deep gluteal compartment may replace or reduce prolonged manual pompage work;
5. the desired effect is not simple stretching, but tone modulation;
6. after complete treatment, recurrence of the block appears rare and mainly related to new traumatic events;
7. a vulnerability of the deep gluteal compartment may nevertheless persist, especially in sedentary subjects;
8. local gluteal maintenance may reduce the frequency of flare-ups;

9. in some gluteal flare-ups, a thoracolumbar-gluteal component may be associated, with lateral tenderness at the last thoracic vertebrae or thoracolumbar junction, without true recurrence of the iliosacral block.

Conclusion

Lumbopelvic dysfunction associated with deep gluteal pain may be interpreted as an integrated pattern in which the articular and tonic-proprioceptive components influence each other.

Manual release represents the first phase of correction, but the stability of the result also appears to depend on reduction of tone in the psoas, piriformis and deep gluteal compartment.

The use of EVM with decreasing frequencies of 50-40-30 Hz, applied after manual correction, may represent a useful strategy to reduce defensive tone, improve load tolerance and limit functional recurrence.

The distinction between true recurrence of the block, deep gluteal flare-up and gluteal flare-up with thoracolumbar-gluteal component allows more precise patient management: the first pattern requires a new lumbopelvic evaluation, whereas the others require work mainly on tone, mobility, the deep gluteal compartment and the thoracolumbopelvic chain.